

WILLINGNESS THE TEACHER ELEMENTARY SCHOOLS FOR INCLUSION IN REGULAR CLASSES IN THE MUNICIPALITY OF BELGRADE (SERBIA REPUBLIC)

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ABSTRACT

The aim of this work is to determine the readiness of primary schools, "Josif Pancic" and "Dragojlo Dudic "for inclusion in regular classes 1st to 4th grade. Research method is analytical and descriptive, prospective study. The research was conducted in the school year 2011/2012 of 46 fourth grade teachers in an urban elementary school, "Josif Pancic" and rural elementary school "Dragojlo Dudic" in Belgrade. In paper is applied technique of interviewing, questionnaire for teachers, Save the Children "UK office in Belgrade, non-governmental organization. Results of distribution of teachers at both schools on inclusion undoubtedly tell us that teachers represent a selective approach to the inclusion of the type and severity of developmental disorders, we might interpret as a positive attitude towards the partial inclusion of the two schools. The obtained conclusions are a guideline for the proposed measures for the prevention and correction of the educational activities of schools and teachers working with children with special needs.

Key words: *Children with special needs, inclusion, Teachers, Elementary School*

1. INTRODUCTION

Individual research studies dealing with the study inclusion and introduction of children with special needs in mainstream schools have shown the importance of encouraging positive attitudes and value orientations of all the participants of the educational process. **[1]**

The results of these studies often point to the existence of non accepting atmosphere in schools (when it comes to inclusive education) and are quite consistent in terms of explanation of the origin of negative attitudes. As a particularly important determinant of these authors in the process of inclusion in mainstream classes, taking the views of the

teachers and students, including a direct participants in the educational process, to a large extent on the successful adaptation of children with special needs in regular classes.

One of the main reasons for their formation can be seen in the lack of personal contact with children who have special needs, then the lack of information from the teacher about the problems that this category child has, opportunities, rights, similarities and specificities compared to children with typical development. As particularly important determinants of the process of inclusion in mainstream classes, singled out the attitudes of teachers and students. Teachers and students as direct participants in the educational process influence largely on the successful adaptation of children with special needs in the regular classroom.

In developed countries in the last twenty years, there is a trend of inclusive education. Inclusion goal is to change the school, not the characteristics of the child. Inclusive education means that you need to fully meet the needs of diverse learners in the regular classroom. All students should be provided with appropriate educational programs adapted to their individual capacities and needs of children. The philosophy of inclusion is not only about education, but considering the successful participation in family and social life flows. [2]

The existence of strategic documents related to those in need of special support is a basic starting point. The first is the strategic document on the reform of the education of students who need special support, passed 2003 rd by the Ministry of Education and Sports of the Republic of Serbia. Ministry of Education and Sports of the Republic of Serbia, which provides guidelines for the organization of various forms of their education, including an inclusive form of a dominant position. During the elaboration of this strategy and the adoption of an action program in the Institute for the Advancement of Education. [3] This large and important topic was our motivation and encouragement in this paper to examine how teachers and class teachers in our study Primary School, "Josif Pancic" and "Dragojlo Dudic" in Belgrade willing to accept a child with special needs in regular classes.

Examining the willingness of these actors in the educational process, we sought to determine whether their views on the participation of children with special needs in the regular school life, obstacles or encouraging factor or incentive for an inclusive process in these schools as well as in general in our country.

2. METHODS

In order to test statistical hypotheses, we used the relevant parametric and non-parametric statistical methods, SPSS 17 program.

Besides descriptive display of frequencies and percentages of the relevant variables in the analysis of the relationship between the independent and dependent variables used the chi-square test when tested hypotheses about the probability distribution categorical variables, the Pearson correlation coefficient of correlation coefficient and the corresponding association. Given the need summary of individual survey questions for teachers will be implemented factor of analysis which Anova is shown that it makes sense to place the issues, the claims are treated as a single variable.

Comparing the results of the survey of these schools will be very important information for the topic you of research. The research results are presented in the form of tables and graphs are interpreted in accordance with the goals, objectives and research hypotheses.

The results were correlated with the available results of similar studies, and the theoretical opinions of authors who were engaged in research of this issue.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The study was carried out in the academic year 2011/2012 of 46 fourth grade teachers in an urban elementary school „Josif Pancic "and a rural primary school „Dragojlo Dudic" in Belgrade. Applied the technique of interviewing, questionnaire for teachers, Save the Children "UK office in Belgrade, non-governmental organizations.

Picture 1. Distribution opinions of teacher in two schools related to inclusion

Distribution opinions of teachers at both schools on inclusion undoubtedly tells us that teachers represent a selective approach to the inclusion of the type and severity of developmental disorders, which we can interpret as a positive attitude towards the partial inclusion of the two schools with (68.1%) and 32 teachers. Eight of the teachers responded positively to your boot issue related to inclusion in regular schools (17%), while six of them (12.8%) had the view that inclusion in mainstream schools utopia in our conditions. The survey did not answer one teacher (2.1%) (Figure 1).

In explaining their responses, teachers relied primarily on the lack of preparedness of schools and teachers for the inclusive process, and as a special issue mentioned the issue of assessment, pointing out that descriptive assessment should be one of the first measures in the preparation of the entire education system when the inclusion concerned.

Question that arises is whether this attitude of teachers should be interpreted as a negative attitude towards inclusion or as an opinion of the surveyed teachers about the actual realization of inclusive processes in our country. Starting from the principle of individual approach to teaching that enable greater differentiation among students of what they learn,

how they learn and what materials are used in accordance with their abilities, aptitudes and interests, we wanted to examine how teachers perceive opportunities for children with special needs in the context of the adoption of regular material.

Further explanation of teacher talking to the researchers themselves were mostly reduced to the realization that our current system of education does not exist for the acceptance of children with special needs, and especially big problem is the complete lack of training teachers to work with this category of children. [4]

According to Vujacic, the 2006 survey shows the existence of the inadequate conditions in our mainstream schools to implement inclusion. It is a sample of 97 mainstream primary schools in Serbia with 8099 students with special needs, found that the number of children for only 20 full-time employees as a special education teacher associates in a given school.

Furthermore, the lack of records of students with special needs, as well as monitoring their development, and education of teachers working with children with special needs, aggravated an inclusive process and slows it in Republic of Serbia. [5] Creating questions on which we put forward some conclusions, attention was paid to the analysis of teachers' sample to this problem, namely:

1. Attitudes of teacher education to children with special needs in mainstream schools,
2. Attitudes of teachers to the classroom teaching children with special needs.

Similar results are received by Gamaz in 2004, where her research showed also that the willingness of teachers to accept children with special needs, depending on the type and severity of disability or disorder . This research shows that teachers are least willing to accept children with sensory disorders, and a better attitude when it comes to children with physical disabilities, emotional problems and chronic diseases. [6]

Picture 2. Distribution of responses of teacher of both schools to the question whether the conditions for the inclusion of children with special needs in their schools

Starting from the principle of individual approach of teaching that enable greater differentiation among students of what they learn, how they learn and what materials are used in accordance with their abilities, aptitudes and interests, we wanted to examine how

teachers perceive opportunities for children with special needs in the context of the adoption of regular material. The claim that the set of regular school classes may include children with special needs in accordance with their abilities to master the regular curriculum, we can see that 28 teachers (49.5%) partially agree with this statement, it is uncertain for 8 teachers or (17%). Six teachers or (12.8%) noted that they do not agree with inclusion of children with special needs in their schools. (Figure 2). These data tell us and confirm the existing definition, which we have mentioned in the theoretical part of this is that education is not inclusion successfully, but the manner and method in which this process is carried out.

Therefore, the question of architectural barriers and their removal as well as serious questions about the organization of life in society in general are mentioned as topics. While answering this question in the survey teachers were at their schools where they work and where we conducted our research, so that the responses indicate that the conditions for the inclusion of children with special needs, of course, vary from school to school. Research we found a very high correlation between the responses of teacher of both schools to the question whether there are conditions for the inclusion of children with special needs in their school ($p = .000$). With the answer of (59.6%) and 28 teachers are partially agrees to the conditions in their home schools for inclusion and integration of children with special needs in mainstream schools. This fact indicates that our schools are not sufficiently prepared for full inclusion in regular schools.

Also, when it comes to inclusion in Republic of Serbia, Novi Sad Humanitarian Center survey from 2008 showed that the most significant determinant of inclusive processes exactly the type and degree of disorder the child has. **[7]** The teaching and professional staff of primary schools in Novi Sad has mostly supported the initiative of the massive involvement of Rome in mainstream schools, which is evident in our study, as well as acceptance of children with motor disabilities, children with behavior disorders and children with sensory disorders. Turning slightly mentally retarded children into regular schools is less accepted, and the greatest resistance to the acceptance of children with autism.

According to Hrnjica in 2005, positive changes in attitudes regarding inclusion has to be done in parallel with all other necessary and changes such as methodological innovations in teaching that are appropriate for their children so the children with typical development and children with special needs, a clear positive attitude Ministry of Education and Sports of the Republic of Serbia. **[8]** Inspectors who evaluated the positive commitment of teachers to work with children with special needs, the introduction of programs aimed at better understanding needs of the children as well as effective assistance to this category of children in schools for teachers and teacher training college. **[9]**

Picture 3. Connection between the two schools and the negative impact of inclusion

On the question of whether a child with special needs in regular classes their schools could have a negative impact on the success of the whole class, teachers are more (51.1%) and 24 of them responded that they partially agree with that statement. In the study we found no statistically significant correlation between the responses of teachers of both schools and the negative impact of the inclusion of children in mainstream schools ($p = .042$) (Table 1).

4. CONCLUSION

These data show once again and confirms the view that inclusive education is not in itself a priori successfully, but the decisive way in which it is implemented. Only the inclusion of children with special needs in mainstream school does not provide any guarantee that it will be in that environment and successfully. Creating opportunities for a successful inclusion involves a change in attitudes and value orientations of participants in the educational process as well as a number of changes in methodological and organizational aspects. **[10]**

So in conclusion we can state that the possibility of a positive inclusive education in our schools, in connection necessary changes and innovations in teaching, training teachers, better school facilities, involvement of a large number of special education teachers in regular schools in the distribution of our survey respondents to be positively correlated the willingness of teachers to accept children with special needs in mainstream schools.

The obtained conclusions are a guideline for the proposed measures for the prevention and correction of the educational activities of the family in order to prevent onset of school failure that occurs as a result of this group cause and correction of the schools and teachers working with children with special needs. Proposals of teachers to better performance in school with children who have special needs, starting with proposals for different educational goals

recommended by teachers or 33 (70.2%), and other organized classes with the response of teachers with 38 or (80.9%), which implies that the teacher in the classroom should the continued presence of an assistant, adequate textbooks, and the presence of special teachers in each department who works at the school or who visits once a week

As suggestions for better work with children with special needs teachers have pointed to an adequate adaptation of school and school equipment with the answer and 28 teachers, or (59, 6%). A number of teachers and 31 (66%) suggested professional development seminars, which would enable them to become more familiar with different characteristics and needs of children who have special needs compared to children with typical development. teachers are also schools that we surveyed believe that this type of training is very complex and is not limited to one or two seminars, but a certain number of continuing education according to the needs of schools in which we conducted our research, as well as the categorization of children with special needs are given in schools.

A small number of students in the department's recommendation of a number of teachers and 31 (66%), and 33 or (70.2%) of the teachers from the schools we surveyed requested a proposal for measures reducing the curriculum when it comes to children with special needs. We felt that this type of information from the teachers themselves can contribute significantly to getting to know the characteristic of the current "inclusive education.

In our research we found a statistically significant association between the elementary school „Josif Pancic "and teachers of this school (23) and problems with the teachers of this school educational goals for children with special needs ($p = .042$).

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